

IMPACT OF NOISE IN SHALLOW QUANTUM CIRCUITS

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1 Abstract

Noises produce result errors in quantum circuits and deprive the proved computational advantage of the quantum algorithms. We are interested in the relation between the result errors and the noises, and investigate the factors that could potentially increase the impact of noise in quantum circuits. Specifically, for those shallow quantum circuits (SQC) which were recently claimed to be less susceptible to noises.

In this report, we set the famous “magic square problem” as the subject. We first present its description, its classical solution, and its quantum solution by SQC. Build upon that, the SQC is simulated on Qiskit simulator and experimented on a real IBM quantum computer with the noises identified. From the results, the impact of total noise and each individual noise in SQC are analysed. The analysis shows that large circuit depth and number of Controlled-NOT gates are the main push factors for large impact of noise in SQC, and they are aggravated by certain limitations of the existing IBM quantum computers including imperfect transpilation, limited qubit connectivity, larger error parameters and longer gate duration originated from the superconducting design approach.

2 Introduction and literature review

Since the idea was first brought to front by R. Feynman [1], quantum computing has shown a strong tendency in reforming the entire field of information with the advent of quantum algorithms capable of efficiently performing computational tasks that were believed to be extremely hard for the classical computing. The most well-known example of such quantum algorithms is the Shor's algorithm for solving prime factorization of large integer N with $O(\log N)$ complexity [2]. Although the achievements of former researchers in theoretical aspects are appreciated, further work required in practical aspects are indispensable for successfully realizing the expected quantum advantage.

One of the forefront practical difficulties is the noise. As open systems, real quantum systems are bound to be affected by the noises from the environment [3]. For a quantum computer that performs quantum algorithms, if the impact of noise is too significant, large amount of information errors will emerge and the expected quantum advantage will disappear.

Quantum algorithms are normally modelled and implemented as quantum circuits. A quantum circuit in generic sense is shown by Figure 1. It consists of quantum bits (qubits), initial qubit states, quantum logic gates, final qubit states, measurements and the classical outputs. The time for maintaining the quantum states of the qubits is the "coherent time". Characteristics such as circuit depth (number of logic gates or time steps on the longest path) and circuit width (number of bits) for classical circuits are transferable to quantum circuits, they are both important considerations for designing a quantum algorithm.

Figure 1: Quantum circuit

For decades in the past and even today, insufficient coherent time of the qubits in the quantum computers without error-correction had motivated the design of new quantum algorithms or the redesign of the past quantum algorithms for the purpose of dispensing with circuit depth and exploiting more circuit width. Researchers believe that by reducing the circuit depth, the circuit can be executed within the available coherent time of the qubits, so that the impact of noise and the circuit error rate are minimized. Figure 2 from a study of T. Lubinski et al. [4] also illustrates the feasibility of this idea. The simulation was done on Qiskit simulator with a quantum volume (QV) of 32, where the QV value quantifies the largest random quantum circuit of equal width and depth that the simulator successfully implements [5]. In Figure 2, the horizontal axis stands for the circuit depth and the vertical axis stands for the circuit width. Each box represents a quantum circuit with specific circuit depth and circuit width, the colour of the box corresponds to the average result fidelity of the circuit which can also be interpreted as: 1 - average result error rate. We can see that the average result fidelity decreases with increase in the circuit depth while stays almost constant with increase in the circuit width.

Figure 2: Benchmark results from IBM simulator with quantum volume (QV) of 32 [4]

In year 2018, research of S. Bravyi et al. [6] established that if the quantum algorithm is designed to have low and constant circuit depth, it still shows advantage over its classical counterpart in performing certain computational tasks without considering noises. They named such quantum circuits the “shallow quantum circuits (SQC)”. Followed by year 2020, another research of the same group [7] further established that the quantum algorithm modelled by SQC shows advantage over its classical counterpart even with the presence of noise. However, the preconditions for obtaining this conclusion are strict. These could include 3D qubit architecture, error-correction coding, and state preparation algorithms. Furthermore, only Pauli errors are taken as example of noise in [7].

This gives rise to our interest in whether the advantage for SQC in the presence of noise persists when the aforementioned preconditions are removed, and in particular, the impact of other types of noises in SQC. Based on those interests, we first describe one of the computational problems from [7], the magic square problem, with its classical solution and quantum solution by SQC. Then, we identify and describe each noise for IBM quantum computers specifically. Finally, we build the SQC in Qiskit for simulation with each individual noise and experimenting on a real IBM quantum computer with total noise. We finish the report by analysing the obtained results and discussing the impact of each individual noise.

3 Goals and objectives

3.1 Overall goal

Overall, this project is aimed at building a SQC, identifying the noises and investigating the impact of noises in the SQC built.

3.2 Specific goals and objectives

1. To build SQC for ideal simulations, noisy simulations and noisy experiments
 - To select and describe a suitable computational problem
 - To interpret the problem into SQC on Qiskit
2. To identify the noises that affecting IBM quantum computers and build noise models
 - To identify the sources of noise and their corresponding error functions in Qiskit
 - To build noise models for each individual noise identified
3. To investigate the impact of noise in the SQC
 - To experiment SQC on a real IBM quantum computer with total noise
 - To simulate SQC on Qiskit simulator ideally and then with individual noise models applied
 - To analyse the experiment and simulation results

4 Background theory

In this chapter, the required background theories by this project in the scope of quantum computing are presented.

4.1 Bra-Ket notation

A standard notation for indicating an object v as a vector is the “Ket” notation $|v\rangle$.

$$\hat{v} = |v\rangle \quad (1)$$

In definition [3], for a complex vector $|v\rangle$ in a complex vector space V , it can be written in the form:

$$|v\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} v_i |i\rangle \quad (2)$$

where n is the dimension of V , v_i is a set of complex numbers,

$$V \in \mathbb{C}^2, \quad v_i \in \mathbb{C} \quad (3)$$

and $|i\rangle$ is the orthonormal (orthogonal and normalized) basis for V . Orthogonal means that the pairwise dot product between different $|i\rangle$ equals to 0, and normalized means that the norm of each $|i\rangle$ is 1.

For example, a complex vector $|v\rangle$ in a two-dimensional complex vector space V can be written as:

$$|v\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^1 v_i |i\rangle = v_0 |0\rangle + v_1 |1\rangle \quad (4)$$

where the matrix representations for $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are:

$$|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, |1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

For complex vector $|v\rangle$ again, there exists a complex conjugate vector $\langle v|$ dual to it, where the standard notation $\langle |$ is called “Bra”. For example, since the matrix representation $|v\rangle$ shown in Eq.(4) is:

$$|v\rangle = v_0 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + v_1 \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} v_0 \\ v_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The matrix representation for $\langle v|$ will be:

$$\langle v| = v_0^* (1 \ 0) + v_1^* (0 \ 1) = (v_0^* \ v_1^*) \quad (7)$$

where $*$ means the complex conjugate.

4.2 Inner product

Complex vectors $|v\rangle$ and $|w\rangle$ of the dimension n from a complex vector space U can be written in matrix representations as:

$$|v\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} v_0 \\ \vdots \\ v_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}, |w\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} w_0 \\ \vdots \\ w_{n-1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$U \in \mathbb{C}^n, \quad v_i, w_i \in \mathbb{C} \quad (9)$$

An inner product of $|v\rangle$ and $|w\rangle$ outputs the pairwise dot product of v_i^* and w_i of $|v\rangle$ and $|w\rangle$.

$$\langle v | (|w\rangle) = (v_0^* \quad \cdots \quad v_{n-1}^*) \begin{pmatrix} w_0 \\ \vdots \\ w_{n-1} \end{pmatrix} = v_0^* w_0 + \cdots + v_{n-1}^* w_{n-1} \quad (10)$$

The corresponding complex vector $|\psi\rangle$ including each product term in the sum shown in Eq.(10) can have matrix representation:

$$|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} v_0^* w_0 \\ \vdots \\ v_{n-1}^* w_{n-1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$v_i^* w_i \in \mathbb{C} \quad (12)$$

The complex vector space H spanned by $|\psi\rangle$ is named as an n -dimensional ‘‘Hilbert space’’ or more commonly as an n -dimensional ‘‘state space’’.

$$H \in \mathbb{C}^n \quad (13)$$

A standard representation of the inner product shown by Eq.(10) is:

$$\langle v | (|w\rangle) = \langle v | w \rangle \quad (14)$$

4.3 Qubit

In analogy with a classical bit as a unit for storing classical information, a qubit (quantum bit) acts as a unit for storing quantum information. Each qubit is a smallest fundamental quantum system with infinite number of quantum states. All those states take the form of a complex vector $|\psi\rangle$ as shown by Eq.(11) with dimension $n=2$ in a two-dimensional state space H .

$$|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} v_0^* w_0 \\ v_1^* w_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$H \in \mathbb{C}^2, \quad v_i^* w_i \in \mathbb{C} \quad (16)$$

Denoting $v_0^*w_0$ by a and $v_1^*w_1$ by b , and transforming $|\psi\rangle$ back to the form as shown in Eq.(2), a standard expression for any states of a qubit can be obtained as:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i=0}^1 v_i^* w_i |i\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle \quad (17)$$

To enable all states normalized, a and b should satisfy $|a|^2 + |b|^2 = 1$, in which $|a|^2$ gives the probability of getting 0, and $|b|^2$ gives the probability of getting 1 after measuring the qubit. More details of measurements are discussed in Section 4.7. Usually, when a qubit has state $|\psi\rangle$ with $|a|^2$ or $|b|^2 \neq 1$, it is said to be in “superposition”.

Orthonormal basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are commonly called the computational basis states or Z-basis states analogous to two distinct states 0 and 1 of a classical bit. Based on that, Y-basis states $|R\rangle$ and $|L\rangle$ can be defined in the form of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ as:

$$|R\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle + i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |L\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle - i|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (18)$$

X-basis states $|+\rangle$ and $|-\rangle$ can be defined in the form of $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ as:

$$|+\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad |-\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (19)$$

A Bloch sphere [8] as shown by Figure 3 can be a perfect visual and mathematical representation of the state space of a qubit, in which X-axis and Z-axis are real axes while Y-axis is imaginary axis. All the states of the qubit are positioned at the surface the sphere with radius being 1, where a and b can be expressed as:

$$a = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right), \quad b = e^{i\phi} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \quad (20)$$

Figure 3: Bloch sphere [8]

4.4 Tensor product

If two n -dimensional state spaces U and V are put together to form a composite n^2 -dimensional state space W , a tensor product with standard notation \otimes is needed.

$$W = U \otimes V \quad (21)$$

$$U, V \in \mathbb{C}^n, \quad W \in \mathbb{C}^{n^2} \quad (22)$$

For example, let a two-dimensional state space U have states $|\psi_1\rangle = a_1|0\rangle + b_1|1\rangle$ and another two-dimensional state space V have states $|\psi_2\rangle = a_2|0\rangle + b_2|1\rangle$, states $|\psi_3\rangle$ that spans the four-dimensional state space W can then be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_1\rangle \otimes |\psi_2\rangle &= a_1|0\rangle + b_1|1\rangle \otimes a_2|0\rangle + b_2|1\rangle \\ &= a_1a_2|00\rangle + a_1b_2|01\rangle + b_1a_2|10\rangle + b_1b_2|11\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where the terms with tensor product notation such as $a_1|0\rangle \otimes a_2|0\rangle$ can be abbreviated to $a_1a_2|00\rangle$. In matrix representation, terms of composite states such as $|00\rangle$ in those abbreviated terms can be expressed as:

$$|00\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1|0\rangle \\ 0|0\rangle \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

4.5 Quantum logic gate

In quantum circuits, operators on qubits are denoted as quantum operators or quantum logic gates analogous to the classical logic gates on classical bits in classical circuits. They can be classified by the number of qubits they manipulate [3].

The single-qubit gates involved in this report are:

Pauli X-gate: $\text{---}\boxed{X}\text{---}$ or $\text{---}\oplus\text{---}$

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0| \quad (25)$$

Pauli Y-gate: $\text{---}\boxed{Y}\text{---}$

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix} = -i|0\rangle\langle 1| + i|1\rangle\langle 0| \quad (26)$$

Pauli Z-gate: $\text{---}\boxed{Z}\text{---}$

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 0| - |1\rangle\langle 1| \quad (27)$$

Pauli I-gate (Identity gate): $\text{---}\boxed{I}\text{---}$

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 1| \quad (28)$$

Phase gate:

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 0| + i|1\rangle\langle 1| \quad (29)$$

Hadamard gate:

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 0| + |0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 1|) \quad (30)$$

Rz gate:

$$Rz(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i\frac{\theta}{2}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\frac{\theta}{2}} \end{pmatrix} = e^{-i\frac{\theta}{2}}|0\rangle\langle 0| + e^{i\frac{\theta}{2}}|1\rangle\langle 1| \quad (31)$$

SX gate:

$$\sqrt{X} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1+i & 1-i \\ 1-i & 1+i \end{pmatrix} = e^{-i\frac{\pi}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) (|0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 1| - i|0\rangle\langle 1| - i|1\rangle\langle 0|) \quad (32)$$

When applying a single-qubit gate to a qubit, the inner product as described in Section 4.2 is taken between the gate and the state of the qubit to give the evolved state. For example, applying Pauli-X gate to a qubit with initial state $|0\rangle$ gives state:

$$X|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = (|0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0|)|0\rangle = |1\rangle \quad (33)$$

Converting matrix representations of single-qubit gates into diagonal representations facilitates manual calculation. In **Appendix A**, an example of deriving the diagonal representation of Pauli-X gate is shown.

Note that the eigenvectors $|v_i\rangle$ of X is exactly the same as X-basis states $|+\rangle$ and $|-\rangle$ as defined by Eq.(19). In fact, the eigenvectors of Y is the same as Y-basis states $|R\rangle$ and $|L\rangle$ as defined by Eq.(18) and the eigenvectors of Z is the same as Z-basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$. These synonymies will be used frequently in the following sections.

The double-qubit gates involved in this report are:

Controlled-NOT gate:

$$\begin{aligned} CNOT &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & X \end{pmatrix} \\ &= |0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes I + |1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes X \\ &= |00\rangle\langle 00| + |01\rangle\langle 01| + |11\rangle\langle 10| + |10\rangle\langle 11| \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 CZ &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & Z \end{pmatrix} \\
 &= |0\rangle\langle 0| \otimes I + |1\rangle\langle 1| \otimes Z \\
 &= |00\rangle\langle 00| + |01\rangle\langle 01| + |10\rangle\langle 10| - |11\rangle\langle 11|
 \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 SWAP &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & X \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & X \end{pmatrix} \\
 &= CNOT(I \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0| + X \otimes |1\rangle\langle 1|)CNOT \\
 &= CNOT(|00\rangle\langle 00| + |01\rangle\langle 11| + |10\rangle\langle 10| + |11\rangle\langle 01|)CNOT \\
 &= |00\rangle\langle 00| + |01\rangle\langle 10| + |11\rangle\langle 11| + |10\rangle\langle 01|
 \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

For Controlled-NOT gate and Controlled-Z gate above specifically, the first qubit at the top is called the “control qubit” while the second qubit at the bottom is called the “target qubit” [3]. When the control qubit has a state $|0\rangle$, the single-qubit gate is not applied to the target qubit, whereas when the control qubit has a state $|1\rangle$, the single-qubit gate is applied to the target qubit.

When applying a double-qubit gate to two qubits, the inner product as described in Section 4.2 is taken between the gate and the composite state of the two-qubit composite system. For example, applying Controlled-Not gate to two-qubit composite system with initial composite state $|00\rangle$ gives:

$$\begin{aligned}
 CNOT|00\rangle &= (|00\rangle\langle 00| + |01\rangle\langle 01| + |11\rangle\langle 10| + |10\rangle\langle 11|)|00\rangle \\
 &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \\
 &= |00\rangle
 \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

After introducing the relevant quantum logic gates, we now introduce the concept of “unitary”.

A unitary quantum logic gate satisfies two requirements. Firstly, the inner product of the unitary quantum logic gate U and its Hermitian conjugate U^\dagger is equivalent to I . Secondly, they obey the commutative law [9].

$$UU^\dagger = U^\dagger U = I \tag{38}$$

The Hermitian conjugate stands for the transposed and the complex conjugate.

$$U^\dagger = (U^*)^T \quad (39)$$

Among all the quantum logic gates which we have just introduced, all single-qubit gates and the Controlled-NOT gate are unitary.

4.6 Density operator (Density matrix)

The representation for any states of a qubit as shown by Eq.(17) is also called the “state-vector representation”. The state-vector representation is comparatively more complicated for describing qubit measurement, and is only suitable for describing the dynamics of the closed quantum systems which are not affected by noises. Therefore, before moving on to introduce the qubit measurement and the noise, we first introduce another representation for any states of a qubit, which is known as the “density operator representation” or “density matrix representation”.

The density operator representation for a qubit is defined as:

$$\rho = \sum_{i=0}^1 p_i |i\rangle\langle i| = \sum_{i=0}^1 p_i \rho_i \quad (40)$$

where p_i is the probability of the state of the qubit being ρ_i .

The evolution of the state of the qubit is defined as:

$$\rho' = U\rho U^\dagger \quad (41)$$

where ρ' is the evolved state of the qubit, U is the unitary operator or unitary quantum logic gate and U^\dagger is the Hermitian conjugate of U .

Thus, for example, applying Pauli-X gate to the qubit gives: The evolution of the state of the qubit with initial state $\rho = |0\rangle\langle 0|$ will be:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho' &= X\rho X^\dagger \\ &= (|0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0|)|0\rangle\langle 0|(|0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0|) \\ &= |1\rangle\langle 1| \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

The definition of tensor product as introduced in Section 4.4 is directly applicable to density operator representation. For example, the composite system ρ_{AB} formed by a qubit with state ρ_A and another qubit with state ρ_B is:

$$\rho_{AB} = \rho_A \otimes \rho_B \quad (43)$$

4.7 Measurement

The circuit symbol for the measurement of a qubit in the quantum circuit is

The single line on the left of the box implies that the state prior to the measurement is quantum, while the double line on the right of the box implies that the state after the

measurement is classical. As the symbol suggests, infinite number of quantum states in a qubit collapse into a definite classical state in a classical bit after measurement.

Measurement is described by a collection of measurement operators $\{M_m\}$ which is similar to quantum operators or quantum logic gates, where m refers to the possible measurement results [3]. Recall that in Section 4.3, three collections of basis states for a qubit are introduced, including Z-basis states $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$, Y-basis states $\{|R\rangle, |L\rangle\}$ and X-basis states $\{|+\rangle, |-\rangle\}$. This implies that the measurement of a qubit can be made in three measuring basis: Measuring in Z-basis output $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$; Measuring in Y-basis output $\{|R\rangle, |L\rangle\}$; Measuring in X-basis output $\{|+\rangle, |-\rangle\}$. Based on that, the collection of measurement operators for measuring in Z-basis is defined as:

$$\{M_m\} = \{M_0, M_1\} = \{|0\rangle\langle 0|, |1\rangle\langle 1|\} \quad (44)$$

The collection of measurement operators for measuring in Y-basis is defined as:

$$\{M_m\} = \{M_R, M_L\} = \{|R\rangle\langle R|, |L\rangle\langle L|\} \quad (45)$$

The collection of measurement operators for measuring in X-basis is defined as:

$$\{M_m\} = \{M_+, M_-\} = \{|+\rangle\langle +|, |-\rangle\langle -|\} \quad (46)$$

Nevertheless, as Z-basis is the default measuring basis for the qubit, transformation processes denoted by specific quantum logic gates are required to enable other measuring bases such as X-basis and Y-basis. An example of transforming the measuring basis from Z-basis to X-basis is shown in **Appendix B**.

Collectively, Table 1 shows the quantum logic gates required for transforming the measuring basis of a single qubit from Z-basis to other measuring bases.

Initial measuring basis	Final measuring basis	Required quantum logic gate
Z	Z	I
Z	X	H
Z	Y	HS^\dagger

Table 1: Quantum logic gates for transforming the measuring basis from Z-basis to other bases

If the state of the qubit is ρ prior to measurement, the probability $p(m)$ for obtaining result m is defined as:

$$p(m) = \text{tr}(M_m^\dagger M_m \rho) \quad (47)$$

The state ρ' of the qubit after the measurement that obtained result m is defined as:

$$\rho' = \frac{M_m \rho M_m^\dagger}{\text{tr}(M_m^\dagger M_m \rho)} = \frac{M_m \rho M_m^\dagger}{p(m)} \quad (48)$$

where $\text{tr}()$ is the function that output the trace (the sum of the diagonal elements) of a matrix.

We have seen the measurement for a single qubit and we have also seen the tensor product in Section 4.4. This leads to tensor measurement, using which the composite states of multiple qubits can be measured. For example, in the case of measuring the composite system of two qubits in composite ZZ-basis, the collection of composite measurement operators will simply be the tensor product of two collection of measurement operators in Z-basis.

$$\begin{aligned}\{M_m\} &= \{M_0, M_1\} \otimes \{M_0, M_1\} = \{M_{00}, M_{01}, M_{10}, M_{11}\} \\ &= \{|00\rangle\langle 00|, |01\rangle\langle 01|, |10\rangle\langle 10|, |11\rangle\langle 11|\}\end{aligned}\quad (49)$$

Another useful property of the tensor measurement is that it allows measurement of a qubit, while keeping other qubits in the same composite system still in the mixed state. For example, measuring a double-qubit composite system in composite ZI basis obtains the results for the first qubit in Z-basis while leave the state of the second qubit intact. Although no measurement is taken, for the convenience of calculation, we still define the measurement operator for the I-basis as:

$$M_m = |I\rangle\langle I| \quad (50)$$

4.8 Entanglement

Entanglement is probably the most notable one of all properties in quantum mechanics, which was likened by Albert Einstein as the “spooky action at a distance”. As commonly stated in quantum computing, entanglement refers to a relation between multiple qubits that the measurement of the state of one qubit will collapse the state of its entangled qubits immediately. One of the most used example for demonstrating entanglement is follows: Considering the case of two separate qubits Q_A and Q_B both with states initialized to $|0\rangle$. Firstly, Q_A is applied with a Hadamard gate, so that it is put into superposition with the state $|\psi_{A0}\rangle$:

$$|\psi_{A0}\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (51)$$

The composite state $|\psi_0\rangle$ of two qubits is therefore:

$$|\psi_0\rangle = \frac{|00\rangle + |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (52)$$

Next, Q_A and Q_B are applied with a Controlled-NOT gate taking Q_A as the control qubit and Q_B as the target qubit. As a result, the composite state $|\psi_0\rangle$ of two qubits is evolved to $|\psi_1\rangle$:

$$|\psi_1\rangle = \frac{|00\rangle + |11\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (53)$$

By Eq.(40), the density operator representation ρ_1 for the state of two qubits at $|\psi_1\rangle$ is:

$$\rho_1 = |\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_1| = \frac{|00\rangle\langle 00| + |00\rangle\langle 11| + |11\rangle\langle 00| + |11\rangle\langle 11|}{2} \quad (54)$$

Now, if we measure only Q_A , which is done by measuring the composite state of two qubits in ZI-basis with the measurement operator $\{M_m\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}\{M_m\} &= \{M_0, M_1\} \otimes |I\rangle\langle I| = \{M_{0I}, M_{1I}\} \\ &= \{|0I\rangle\langle 0I|, |1I\rangle\langle 1I|\}\end{aligned}\tag{55}$$

Using Eq.(47), the probabilities of obtaining each result m are obtained as:

$$p(|0I\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad p(|1I\rangle) = \frac{1}{2}\tag{56}$$

Using Eq.(48), the state ρ'_1 after the measurement that obtained result m are:

$$\rho'_1 = |0I\rangle\langle 0I|, \quad \text{for } m = |0I\rangle\tag{57}$$

$$\rho'_1 = |1I\rangle\langle 1I|, \quad \text{for } m = |1I\rangle\tag{58}$$

Observing Eq.(57) and (58), the state of Q_B is already confirmable. As the state ρ_1 shown by Eq.(54) before the measurement is known, the state of Q_B is immediately $|0\rangle$ if the state of Q_B is measured to be $|0\rangle$ and immediately $|1\rangle$ if the state of Q_B is measured to be $|1\rangle$. Note that even if two qubits are taken to two locations far away from each other, the immediate effect due to entanglement still exists.

5 The magic square problem

In this chapter, the methods and setups for investigating the impact of noise in SQCs are presented. First and foremost, the magic square problem is introduced. Then, the classical solution and the quantum solution by SQC for the problem are described.

5.1 Introduction to the magic square problem

The magic square problem arises from the magic square game which belongs to a class of games called the “non-local games”. For a non-local game, players play against a referee, they are not allowed to communicate with each other which can be considered as a physical constraint due to spatial separation [10]. Recall that the phenomenon of quantum entanglement as introduced in Section 4.8 allows immediate effect on a qubit when we measure its entangled qubit regardless of their spatial separation. Due to entanglement, quantum strategy has the natural advantage in playing these non-local games. Therefore, non-local games are always taken as the focus of the debate for the advantage of quantum algorithms over their classical counterparts.

Back to the magic square game, it involves a referee and two players, Alice and Bob. Alice and Bob can only communicate with the referee, but not with each other. They play the game on a 3 x 3 magic square, like the one shown by Figure 4, where columns and rows are identified using binary numbers equivalent of decimal numbers 1, 2 and 3.

	01	10	11
01			
10			
11			

Figure 4: 3x3 magic square

For each round of a game, Alice chooses a column and Bob chooses a row. They do not know the choice of each other. After that, they must instruct the referee to fill in numbers following specific rules, as follows. Alice fills the column from the top to the bottom with either 1 or 0 complying with having an odd number of 1s (odd parity). Bob fills the row from the left to the right with either 1 or 0 complying with having an even number of 1s (even parity). Finally, if they filled the intersecting box (the box where the column selected by Alice and the row selected by Bob intersect) with the same number, they win this round of the game, as shown by the example Figure 5.

	01	10	11
01		1	
10	1	0	1
11		0	

Figure 5: Example of Alice and Bob winning the game

Based on all these rules, the magic square problem asks: How can two players win the magic square game for 100% probability?

5.2 Mathematical expression of the rules of the magic square game

It is worthwhile to first formulate the rules of the magic square game mathematically before moving on to the solutions of the magic square problem.

Alice and Bob's input bits for specifying their selected row and column are:

$$\alpha_j, \beta_j \in \{0, 1\}^2 \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2 \dots, n \quad (59)$$

where n represents the number of rounds, that is, the number of times Alice and Bob are asked to input their choices of row and column within a set of game. α and β are 2-bit inputs for Alice and Bob in binary equivalent to the numbers 1, 2 and 3 in decimal. Thus, α_j and β_j are the identification (binary numbers) of the column and row selected by Alice and Bob in the j -th round of the game, respectively.

After selecting the column and the row, the first two numbers that Alice and Bob selected to enter are identified as:

$$x_j = (p_{2j-1}, q_{2j-1}), \quad y_j = (p_{2j}, q_{2j}) \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2 \dots, n \quad (60)$$

where x_j is a duple made of the first two numbers Alice selected to enter in the j -th round of the game, p_{2j-1} is the first element of the duple and q_{2j-1} is the second. Likewise, y_j is a duple made of the first two numbers Bob selected to enter in the j -th round of the game, p_{2j} is the first number and q_{2j} is the second. For example, for $n=1$, p_0 and q_0 represent the two first numbers selected by Alice whilst p_1 and q_1 represent the first two numbers selected by Bob. Notice that by selecting the first two numbers, the third number is immediately determined by the parity function because of the rules of Alice/Bob selecting an odd/even number of 1s.

The game is won for the j -th round when:

$$p_{2j-1} \oplus q_{2j-1} \oplus r_{2j-1} = 1 \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2 \dots, n \quad (61)$$

$$p_{2j} \oplus q_{2j} \oplus r_{2j} = 0 \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2 \dots, n \quad (62)$$

$$(p_{2j-1}, q_{2j-1}, r_{2j-1})^{\iota(\beta_j)} = (p_{2j}, q_{2j}, r_{2j})^{\iota(\alpha_j)} \quad (63)$$

where r_{2j-1} is the third number Alice selected to enter in the j -th round of the game, and r_{2j} is the third number Bob selected to enter in the j -th round of the game; $\iota(m)$ is a function that converts a number m from binary to decimal:

$$\iota(\alpha_j), \iota(\beta_j) \in \{1, 2, 3\} \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2 \dots, n \quad (64)$$

and it is used to get the decimal representation of the column/row selected by Alice or Bob; $(p_{2j-1}, q_{2j-1}, r_{2j-1})^{\iota(\beta_j)}$ corresponds to the $\iota(\beta_j)$ -th number in the tuple $(p_{2j-1}, q_{2j-1}, r_{2j-1})$ and $(p_{2j}, q_{2j}, r_{2j})^{\iota(\alpha_j)}$ corresponds to the $\iota(\alpha_j)$ -th number in the tuple (p_{2j}, q_{2j}, r_{2j}) .

Eq.(61) and (62) are parity functions with notation \oplus for modulo 2 calculation, they check the parity of their inputs. Eq.(61) checks that Alice has made a valid selection of numbers (odd number of 1s or odd parity). Analogously, Eq.(62) checks that Bob has made a valid selection of numbers (even number of 1s or even parity). In addition, Eq.(63) checks that Alice and Bob selected the same number for the intersecting box.

5.3 The classical solution of the magic square problem

Classical solutions for solving a computational problem can be classified as deterministic and probabilistic. Deterministic solutions do not use random variables, they produce fixed outputs according to specific inputs. On the opposite, probabilistic solutions use random variables, so the outputs change each time for the same inputs. For example, imagine a person walking from place A to place B. He can choose one of two routes. A deterministic solution could be comparing the distance of both routes and always choosing the shortest one, whereas a probabilistic solution could be tossing a coin with head representing the longest route and tail representing the shortest route.

The magic square problem has neither deterministic nor probabilistic solutions with a probability of success equal to 1, due to the fact that Alice and Bob cannot communicate. An example of a case where Alice and Bob lose a round of the game is the following: in the j -th round, Alice and Bob selected $\alpha_j, \beta_j = 11$ (i.e. rightmost column and lowest row) and the parity of the first two numbers they selected to enter are the same:

$$p_{2j-1} \oplus q_{2j-1} = p_{2j} \oplus q_{2j} \quad (65)$$

In that case, it is not possible to have a third number that allows meeting Eq.(61)-(63). In other word, $r_{2j-1} \neq r_{2j}$ and $(p_{2j-1}, q_{2j-1}, r_{2j-1})^{\iota(\beta_j)} \neq (p_{2j}, q_{2j}, r_{2j})^{\iota(\alpha_j)}$.

An example of this condition is shown by Figure 5. In this case, filling either 0 or 1 into the intersecting box will cause either Eq.(61) or Eq.(62) to be invalid.

	01	10	11
01			0
10			1
11	0	1	?

Figure 6: Example of Alice and Bob losing the game

Applying Lemma 3 in the paper of G. Brassard et al. [11] for such problem having neither deterministic strategies nor probabilistic strategies with 100% probability of success, the next best probability of success ω is calculated to be:

$$\omega = \frac{\#P - 1}{\#P} = \frac{9 - 1}{9} = \frac{8}{9} \quad (66)$$

where $\#P$ denotes the number of legitimate questions for Alice and Bob, these questions are the set of combinations α_j and β_j they could have. The number of elements in this set is 9.

Furthermore, it has been proved in [7] that the classical solution for playing multiple rounds ($n > 1$) in one game requires logarithmically increase in the circuit depth (i.e. logarithmic complexity).

5.4 The quantum solution of the magic square problem

Quantum solution for the magic square problem of a one-round ($n=1$) game is modelled as a SQC as shown in Figure 7 [7].

Figure 7: SQC for the quantum solution of the $n = 1$ magic square problem

In the leftmost part of Figure 7, the input bits and the qubits can be seen. The selection of column and row by Alice and Bob are represented by the two-bit values α_1 and β_1 , respectively. Alice and Bob are both assigned two qubits, Q_0 and Q_1 for Alice, Q_2 and Q_3 for Bob. Each qubit is initialized to state $|0\rangle$, the initial composite state $|\Phi_0\rangle$ for four qubits is therefore:

$$|\Phi_0\rangle = |0000\rangle \quad (67)$$

A Hadamard gate is applied to Q_0 followed by a Controlled-NOT gate taking Q_0 as the control qubit and Q_2 as the target qubit. Likewise, Q_1 and Q_3 go through the same process. As a result, Q_0 and Q_2 , Q_1 and Q_3 are entangled, four qubits are put into superposition:

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi_1\rangle &= [(H_0 \otimes I_2)CNOT_{0,2} \otimes (H_1 \otimes I_3)CNOT_{1,3}]|0000\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(|0000\rangle + |0101\rangle + |1010\rangle + |1111\rangle) \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

where the subscripts on H and I show which qubit they are applied to. First subscript of $CNOT$ indicates the control qubit and the second subscript indicates the target qubit.

After the preparation of the superposition state $|\Phi_1\rangle$, Clifford gates, composed of different quantum logic gates, are applied to transform the measuring basis of each two qubits accordingly.

Table 2 [7] describes the behaviour of the Clifford gates $U(\alpha_1)$ and $V(\beta_1)$ shown in Figure 7 with classical binary input α_1 and β_1 . For example, if Alice selects the leftmost column ($\alpha_1 = 01$), then the Clifford gate $U(\alpha_1)$ becomes the tensor product of a Hadamard gate applied to Q_0 and a Pauli-I gate applied to Q_1 .

α_1, β_1 \diagdown $U(\alpha_1), V(\beta_1)$	$U(\alpha_1)$	$V(\beta_1)$
00	$I_0 \otimes I_1$	$I_2 \otimes I_3$
01	$H_0 \otimes I_1$	$H_2 \otimes H_3$
10	$(H_0 \otimes I_1)SWAP_{0,1}$	$SWAP_{2,3}$
11	$(H_0 \otimes I_1)CNOT_{0,1}$	$(H_2 \otimes H_3)CZ_{2,3}(Z_2 \otimes Z_3)$

Table 2: Clifford gates $U(\alpha_1)$ and $V(\beta_1)$ [7]

Table 3 listed the transformed composite measuring basis for each of two double-qubit composite systems of Alice and Bob as a result of applying classically Controlled Clifford gates $U(\alpha_1)$ and $V(\beta_1)$ being described in Table 2.

α_1, β_1 \diagdown Measuring basis	Alice	Bob
00	$Z_0 \otimes I_1, I_0 \otimes Z_1$	$Z_2 \otimes I_3, I_3 \otimes Z_2$
01	$X_0 \otimes I_1, I_0 \otimes Z_1$	$X_2 \otimes I_3, I_3 \otimes X_2$
10	$I_0 \otimes X_1, Z_0 \otimes I_1$	$I_2 \otimes Z_3, Z_3 \otimes I_2$
11	$X_0 \otimes Z_1$	$Y_2 \otimes Y_3$

Table 3: Transformed measuring basis by $U(\alpha_1)$ and $V(\beta_1)$

After the transformation, four qubits are measured to output first two numbers p_1, q_1, p_2 and q_2 which Alice and Bob will select to enter. They are stored into classical register C_0, C_1, C_2 and C_3 respectively. Alice and Bob then calculate their third numbers r_1 and r_2 using Eq.(61) and Eq.(62).

Taking $\alpha_1, \beta_1 = 01$ as example to clarify the whole process. The Clifford gates $U(\alpha_1)$ and $V(\beta_1)$ are:

$$U(\alpha_1) = H_0 \otimes I_1, \quad V(\beta_1) = H_2 \otimes H_3 \quad (69)$$

They transform the measuring basis of Q_0 and Q_1 to $X_0 \otimes I_1$ followed by $I_0 \otimes Z_1$, and the measuring basis of Q_2 and Q_3 to $X_2 \otimes I_3$ followed by $I_2 \otimes X_3$.

By Eq.(40), the density operator representation ρ_1 of the state of four qubits at $|\Phi_1\rangle$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 &= |\Phi_1\rangle\langle\Phi_1| \\ &= \frac{1}{4}(|0000\rangle\langle 0000| + |0000\rangle\langle 0101| + |0000\rangle\langle 1010| + |0000\rangle\langle 1111| \\ &\quad + |0101\rangle\langle 0000| + |0101\rangle\langle 0101| + |0101\rangle\langle 1010| + |0101\rangle\langle 1111| \\ &\quad + |1010\rangle\langle 0000| + |1010\rangle\langle 0101| + |1010\rangle\langle 1010| + |1010\rangle\langle 1111| \\ &\quad + |1111\rangle\langle 0000| + |1111\rangle\langle 0101| + |1111\rangle\langle 1010| + |1111\rangle\langle 1111|) \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

Then four qubits are then applied with the Clifford gates for transforming the measuring basis. The composite measuring basis for four qubits are $(X_0 \otimes I_1) \otimes (X_2 \otimes I_3)$ followed by $(I_0 \otimes Z_1) \otimes (I_2 \otimes X_3)$. The measuring basis $(X_0 \otimes I_1) \otimes (X_2 \otimes I_3)$ corresponds

to the collection of measuring operators:

$$\begin{aligned}\{M_m\} &= (\{M_+, M_-\} \otimes |I\rangle\langle I|) \otimes (\{M_+, M_-\} \otimes |I\rangle\langle I|) \\ &= \{|+I+I\rangle\langle +I+I|, |+I-I\rangle\langle +I-I|, |-I+I\rangle\langle -I+I|, |-I-I\rangle\langle -I-I|\}\end{aligned}\quad (71)$$

In a similar fashion, the measuring basis $(I_0 \otimes Z_1) \otimes (I_2 \otimes X_3)$ corresponds to the collection of measuring operators:

$$\begin{aligned}\{M_m\} &= (|I\rangle\langle I| \otimes \{M_0, M_1\}) \otimes (|I\rangle\langle I| \otimes \{M_+, M_-\}) \\ &= \{|IOI+\rangle\langle IOI+|, |IOI-\rangle\langle IOI-|, |I1I+\rangle\langle I1I+|, |I1I-\rangle\langle I1I-|\}\end{aligned}\quad (72)$$

Using Eq.(47) and (48), the result m from measuring four qubits and their corresponding non-zero probability $p(m)$ are obtained as:

$$m \in \{0100, 1111, 1110, 1011, 0000, 0001, 0101, 1010\} \quad (73)$$

$$p(m) = \frac{1}{8} \quad (74)$$

The first two bits of m will be the numbers (p_1, q_1) that Alice will enter to the first two boxes of her selected column (column 01) and the last two bits will be the numbers (p_2, q_2) that Bob will enter to the first two boxes of his selected row (row 01).

Since $\alpha_1, \beta_1 = 01$, the intersecting box is their first boxes, Eq.(46) is always satisfied regardless of their third numbers r_1 and r_2 . Thus, Alice and Bob won this round of the game for a 100% probability of success. In fact, for all possible combinations of α_1 and β_1 , the probability of success is always 100%.

For playing multiple rounds ($n > 1$) in a game, the quantum solution requires no increase in the circuit depth, hence only constant complexity which is significantly better than the logarithmic complexity for classical solution aforementioned in Section 5.3. An example of the shallow quantum circuit for $n = 2$ is shown by Figure 8 [7], where Clifford gates $U(\alpha_2)$ and $V(\beta_2)$ are the same as $U(\alpha_1)$ and $V(\beta_1)$ as shown in Table 2. The Clifford gate $W(\beta_1, \alpha_2)$ has the behaviour as shown by Table 4 [7].

β_1, α_2	$W(\beta_1, \alpha_2)$
00	$(H_2 \otimes I_3)CNOT_{2,3} \otimes (H_4 \otimes I_5)CNOT_{4,5}$
otherwise	$I_2 \otimes I_3 \otimes I_4 \otimes I_5$

Table 4: Clifford gate $W(\beta_1, \alpha_2)$ [7]

Figure 8: SQC for the quantum solution of the $n = 2$ magic square problem [7]

6 Noises in IBM quantum computers

In this chapter, the noises in IBM quantum computers are identified, they are noises affecting the IBM quantum computers which are collectively referred to as the device backend noise. It encompasses the gate error, measure error, readout error and reset error, in which the gate error can be breakdown further into depolarizing error and thermal relaxation error [12]. Each noise has its own error function in Qiskit which returns a noise channel represented by a “map” ε . When the quantum system with original quantum state ρ passes through the noise channel, ε performs quantum operations on ρ and outputs an evolved quantum state ρ' .

$$\rho' = \varepsilon(\rho) \quad (75)$$

6.1 Gate error

Gate errors can be further breakdown into depolarizing error and thermal relaxation error. It emerges from the physical imperfections of the quantum logic gates [13].

6.1.1 Depolarizing error

The depolarizing error arises from the bit-flip error and phase-flip error. When a qubit is applied with a quantum logic gate that is physically imperfect, the state of the qubit might be bit-flipped or phase-flipped.

The map for the depolarizing noise channel is:

$$\rho' = \varepsilon(\rho) = \frac{\lambda I^{\otimes N}}{2^N} + (1 - \lambda)\rho \quad (76)$$

where λ is the error parameter and N is the number of the qubits passing through the noise channel. The superscript $\otimes N$ on I indicates the number of I in the tensor product. For example, when $N=2$,

$$I^{\otimes 2} = I \otimes I \quad (77)$$

Through the noise channel, the original quantum state ρ remains unchanged for a probability of $1 - \lambda$, or transformed into a mixed state $\frac{\lambda I^{\otimes N}}{2^N}$ for a probability of λ . Using the equivalence:

$$I = \frac{\rho + X\rho X + Y\rho Y + Z\rho Z}{2} \quad (78)$$

The state ρ' of a single qubit that have passed through the noise channel can be expressed as:

$$\rho' = \varepsilon(\rho) = \frac{\lambda}{4}(X\rho X + Y\rho Y + Z\rho Z) + (1 - \frac{3\lambda}{4})\rho \quad (79)$$

Eq.(79) gives rise to another interpretation of the effect of the noise channel, through which the original state ρ remains unchanged for a probability of $1 - \frac{3\lambda}{4}$, or applied with one of the Pauli-X, Pauli-Y and Pauli-Z gates for a probability of $\frac{\lambda}{4}$. Physically, applied with Pauli-X gate means the qubit is bit-flipped, applied with Pauli-Z gate means the qubit is phase-flipped, and applied with Pauli-Y gate means the qubit is both bit-flipped and phase-flipped [14].

6.1.2 Thermal relaxation error

The thermal relaxation error arises from the thermalization of the qubit spins towards an equilibrium state at the temperature of their environment over the gate duration [13].

The thermal relaxation noise channel is firstly expressed in the form of the Choi matrix Λ . For a single qubit, Λ is:

$$\Lambda = \sum_{i,j=0}^1 |i\rangle\langle j| \otimes \varepsilon(|i\rangle\langle j|) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & e^{-\frac{t}{T_2}} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 - e^{-\frac{t}{T_1}} & 0 \\ e^{-\frac{t}{T_2}} & 0 & 0 & e^{-\frac{t}{T_1}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (80)$$

where t is the gate duration, T_1 is the amplitude damping time, T_2 is the phase damping time, and

$$\varepsilon(|0\rangle\langle 0|) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = |0\rangle\langle 0| \quad (81)$$

$$\varepsilon(|0\rangle\langle 1|) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & e^{-\frac{t}{T_2}} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = e^{-\frac{t}{T_2}} |0\rangle\langle 1| \quad (82)$$

$$\varepsilon(|1\rangle\langle 0|) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ e^{-\frac{t}{T_2}} & 0 \end{pmatrix} = e^{-\frac{t}{T_2}} |1\rangle\langle 0| \quad (83)$$

$$\varepsilon(|1\rangle\langle 1|) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - e^{-\frac{t}{T_1}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-\frac{t}{T_1}} \end{pmatrix} = (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{T_1}}) |0\rangle\langle 0| + e^{-\frac{t}{T_1}} |1\rangle\langle 1| \quad (84)$$

The map for the thermal relaxation noise channel is then defined as:

$$\rho' = \varepsilon(\rho) = \text{tr}_1[\Lambda(\rho^T \otimes I)] \quad (85)$$

where the function $\text{tr}_1()$ gives the partial trace over the qubit affected by the single-qubit thermal relaxation noise.

6.2 Measure error

Measure error can be thought as the bit-flip error that occurs while performing measurement on the qubit. Thus, the map of the measure noise channel is the same as that of the bit-flip noise channel:

$$\rho' = \varepsilon(\rho) = \lambda X \rho X + (1 - \lambda) \rho \quad (86)$$

where λ is the measure error parameter. Through the noise channel, the original quantum state ρ stays constant for a probability of $1 - \lambda$, or being bit-flipped for a probability of λ .

6.3 Readout error

Readout error occurs when recording the results after the measurements. Rather than returning a noise channel that represented by a map, it is modelled as a pair of conditional probabilities $P(j|0)$ and $P(j|1)$ for $j = 0, 1$. By inference, $P(0|0)$ and $P(1|1)$ are the probabilities for recording correctly given the true result, while $P(0|1)$ and $P(1|0)$ are the probabilities for recording incorrectly given the true result. The error parameter λ for the readout error is equivalent to $P(0|1)$ or $P(1|0)$.

6.4 Reset error

Reset error occurs when resetting the state of the qubit to $|0\rangle\langle 0|$ after the measurement so that the quantum circuit can be executed again. The map for the reset noise channel is:

$$\rho' = \varepsilon(\rho) = (1 - p_0)\rho + p_0|0\rangle\langle 0| \quad (87)$$

where p_0 is the probability of resetting the state of the qubit to $|0\rangle\langle 0|$.

Through the noise channel, the original quantum state ρ stays constant for a probability of $1 - p_0$, or reset to $|0\rangle\langle 0|$ for a probability of p_0 . The error parameter λ for the reset error is equivalent to $1 - p_0$.

7 Results, analysis and discussion

After we have prepared the SQC for solving the $n=1$ magic square problem and identified the noises in the IBM quantum computers, in this chapter, the processes of simulating the SQC on Qiskit simulator with each individual noises and experimenting the SQC on a real IBM quantum computer with total noise are described.

The experiment outputs the total SQC result error rates when executed on a real IBM quantum computer that is affected by a combination of all noises.

The simulation outputs the error parameter analysis diagram. It shows the relation between the SQC result error rate and the error parameter λ of single noise in the SQC. Specifically for thermal depolarizing error as shown in Section 6.1.2 that does not have an error parameter, the diagram shows the relation between the SQC result error rate and the gate duration t . From the relation between the SQC result error rate and error parameter of single noises or the gate duration, the contribution of each noises to the total SQC error rate can be revealed.

7.1 Experiment and total SQC result error rate

The experiment is carried out in IBM's Toronto quantum computer which we abbreviate as "Toronto" in the following sections. The reason for choosing Toronto is that it has more than 8 qubits which are the least amount required for carrying out the experiment for $n=2$ magic square problem. During experiment, we execute the SQC of the $n=1$ magic square problem for each different combination of α_1 and β_1 on Toronto, and record the total SQC result error rate corresponds to that particular combination.

The total SQC result error rate obtained from the experiment is shown by Figure 9, where the horizontal axis listed different combinations of α_1 and β_1 , and the vertical axis shows their error rates.

Figure 9: Total SQC result error rate

Every real IBM quantum computer has its own supporting quantum logic gates and qubit architecture or qubit layout. Thus, to comply with the supporting quantum logic gates and make best use of the qubit architecture to optimize the circuit depth and the circuit error rate, an intermediate step called “transpilation” is taken automatically by the transpiler in the quantum computer before implementing the SQC [15]. The supporting quantum logic gates of Toronto include Pauli-I gate, Pauli-X gate, Rz gate, SX gate and Controlled-NOT gate. Hence, after transpilation, the Hadamard gates in the SQC is replaced with:

$$H = Rz\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)\sqrt{X}Rz\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \quad (88)$$

The Pauli-Z gate in the SQC is replaced with:

$$Z = Rz(\pi) \quad (89)$$

The Controlled-Z gate in the SQC is replaced with:

$$CZ_{0,1} = Rz_1\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)\sqrt{X}_1Rz_1\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)CNOT_{0,1}Rz_1\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right)\sqrt{X}_1Rz_1\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \quad (90)$$

The SWAP gate in the SQC is replaced with:

$$SWAP_{0,1} = CNOT_{0,1}CNOT_{1,0}CNOT_{0,1} \quad (91)$$

The qubit architecture of Toronto is shown by Figure 10 [16], with circles representing the qubits, the numbers in the circles representing the indices of the qubits and the sticks representing the connections between the qubits.

Figure 10: Qubit architecture of Toronto [16]

From Figure 10, we can see that Toronto has a 2D qubit architecture with 27 qubits. Each qubits are not locally connected to all other qubits, but only limited number of qubits. For example, qubit 1 is only locally connected to qubit 0, 2 and 4. Therefore, if we want to apply a Controlled-NOT gate on qubit 1 and 3, a SWAP gate needs to be applied to swap qubit 3 to qubit 2. Due to this connectivity limitation, consecutive redundant SWAP gates (triple Controlled-NOT gates as shown by Eq.(91)) might be introduced during the transpilation which seriously increase the depth of the circuit, and lead to higher circuit error rate associated with larger impact of noise. Apart from the number of Controlled-NOT gates, transpilation will not increase the number of single-qubit gates as no connection between qubits are required for applying those single-qubit gates, so we pay more attention to the number of Controlled-NOT gates.

Looking back to Figure 9, we can observe that the SQCs for $\alpha_1 = 10, \beta_1 = 11$ and $\alpha_1 = 11, \beta_1 = 11$ have shown remarkably higher error rates than other cases. Not surprisingly, the reason behind is transpilation. The transpiled SQC corresponding to each combinations of α_1 and β_1 are given in **Appendix C**, and their depths and the number of Controlled-NOT gates are summarized in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Transpiled circuit depth and No. of CNOT gates

Taking both Figure C.6 and C.9 in **Appendix C** and Figure 11 into account, we can see that even if we set the optimization level of the transpiler to maximum, transpilation still increases depth and the number of Controlled-NOT gate of the SQCs for $\alpha_1 = 10, \beta_1 = 11$ and $\alpha_1 = 11, \beta_1 = 11$ to significantly higher levels than the SQCs for other cases. With higher depth and larger number of Controlled-NOT gates, the transpiled SQCs suffer from larger impact of noise.

Another observation from Figure 9 is that the lowest error rate is 0.175. Recall that the best classical solution for the magic square problem has a $\frac{8}{9}$ probability of success, or equivalently a $\frac{1}{9}$ (≈ 0.111) error rate which is clearly lower than 0.175. This indicates that when none of the 3D qubit architecture, error-correction coding and state preparation algorithm as proposed in [7] are available, the quantum solution of the magic square problem by SQC fails to outperform the best classical solution using one of the latest IBM quantum computers, Toronto.

7.2 Simulation and error parameter analysis

The simulation was carried out in Qiskit simulator. The aim for the simulation is to find out the contribution of each individual noise to the total SQC result error rate, so in this occasion, only single noise is applied to the SQC each time. The error parameter of the

noises (gate duration for thermal relaxation error specifically) is varied to see how the SQC result error rate varies. The error parameter analysis diagrams corresponding to each choices of α_1 and β_1 for each noises are given in **Appendix D**. Every diagram includes five curves, four of which show the relation between SQC result error rate and the error parameter of depolarizing error, measure error, readout error and reset error, and one of which shows the relation between SQC result error rate and the gate duration of thermal relaxation error. Instead of going through all the diagrams, it is sufficient to focus on two of them which are most representative as they give the lowest and the highest SQC result error rates as shown by Figure 9. They are the diagram for $\alpha_1 = 01$ and $\beta_1 = 10$ as shown by Figure D.2 and the diagram for $\alpha_1 = 10$ and $\beta_1 = 11$ as shown by Figure D.6 in **Appendix D**. Those two diagrams are put together as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Error parameter analysis diagrams for $\alpha_1 = 01$, $\beta_1 = 10$ case and $\alpha_1 = 10$, $\beta_1 = 11$ case put together

We approximate the depolarizing error parameter to be 0.065, the measure error parameter to be 0.05, the readout error parameter to be 0.045 and the gate duration to be $0.45 \mu\text{s}$ in Toronto according to the average values provided in [16]. They are marked on Figure 12 and labelled on the right side of the figure. We can see that measure error and readout error in SQC for $\alpha_1 = 10$ and $\beta_1 = 11$ produce slightly higher SQC result error rate than that in SQC for $\alpha_1 = 01$ and $\beta_1 = 10$. On the other hand, the depolarizing error and thermal relaxation error that compose the gate error produce significantly higher SQC result error rate than that in SQC for $\alpha_1 = 01$ and $\beta_1 = 10$. Since we have seen that the SQC for $\alpha_1 = 10$ and $\beta_1 = 11$ has significantly larger circuit depth and number of Controlled-NOT gates, it is plausible to ascribe the higher total SQC error rate to this reason. Closer inspection also reveals that the the depolarizing error takes a larger proportion of the gate error than the thermal relaxation error.

In fact, even if the circuit depth and the number of Controlled-NOT gates are kept small, Toronto still have excessively high error parameters and long gate duration originated from IBM’s superconducting design approach of their quantum computers [17].

This explains why even the case of the SQC for $\alpha_1 = 01$ and $\beta_1 = 10$ with relatively low circuit depth and small number of Controlled-NOT gates shows a considerably high result error rate of 0.175 when compared to the best classical solution.

Another interesting observation from the error parameter analysis diagrams in **Appendix D** is on reset error. All SQCs are not affected by the reset error. One possible reason for that might be Qiskit simulator assuming the quantum circuit is always correctly reset.

8 Conclusion and future work

To sum up, in this project, one of the computational problem called the “magic square problem” is studied. On the basis of the SQC for its quantum solution, we investigated impact of noises that have been identified. The SQC was experimented on a IBM’s Toronto quantum computer with total noise and simulated on Qiskit simulator with each individual noise. Finally, we obtained the results from the experiment and simulation and analysed the impact of total noise and each individual noise in the SQC. We also discussed the factors that aggravated the result error rate of the SQC.

Three main conclusions can be made from the results as shown in Section 7. The first conclusion is that the transpilation still introduce redundant SWAP gates or Controlled-NOT gate to the SQC even when the optimization level is maximized. As a result, the circuit depth increases. Together, they produce higher impact of noise in SQC. In the future, more works can be done to improve the optimizing algorithm of the transpiler within IBM quantum computers.

The second conclusion is that the quantum solution for the magic square problem by SQC can not outperform the best classical solution when none of the 3D qubit architecture, error-correction coding and state preparation algorithm as proposed in [7] are available. In future works, those pre-conditions and other noise mitigation methods can be researched. In fact, the error-correction coding and state preparation algorithm have already been designed, although they are still in their experimental stage and can not be easily applied. Moreover, the SQC could be implemented on other quantum computers which might not be as freely accessible as the IBM quantum computers. Example could be IonQ and Quantinuum quantum computers which adopt the trapped-ion design approach, or Rigetti quantum computers that adopt the superconducting design approach which is the same for IBM quantum computers. [4] also experimentally compared one latest quantum computer from each of those companies, and the result are shown by Figure 13 which is similar to Figure 2. Observing the region enclosed by pink line in each diagram, it is clear that the IonQ and Quantinuum quantum computers allows high average result fidelities in a wider range of circuit depth and circuit width than IBM and Rigetti quantum computers.

Figure 13: Benchmark results from IonQ, Quantinuum, IBM and Rigetti quantum computers [4]

The third conclusion is that the larger circuit depth and number of Controlled-NOT gate for the transpiled SQCs leads to larger impact of noise. This is contributed by the increase in the impact of all the single noises except the reset error which has no impact throughout the simulation. Among those single noises, the increases in the impact of depolarizing error and thermal relaxation error are most significant, whereas the increases in measure error and readout error which comprise the gate error are slight. In future works, deeper researches into those noises and their physical sources can be made. Focus of the future noise mitigation measures can be placed on restricting the gate error.

Due to the page limit, the SQC for $n=2$ magic square problem which consists of 81 different combinations of α_1 , β_1 , α_2 and β_2 is not shown here. The experiment of the SQC for $n=2$ magic square problem shows that it suffers from more impact of noises compared to $n=1$ case, which further reduced its chance of outperforming the best classical solution. This is, however, in accordance to expectation as the increase in circuit width would certainly increase the number of Controlled-NOT gates due to the need for swapping qubits in IBM quantum computers with limited qubit connectivities. This problem should be able to fixed in the foreseeable future when the qubits for IBM quantum computers are locally connected to all other qubits and the qubit connectivities become strong.

9 References

- [1] R. P. Feynman, “Simulating physics with computers,” *International journal of theoretical physics*, vol. 21, no. 6/7, pp. 467–488, 1982.
- [2] P. W. Shor, “Polynomial-time algorithms for prime factorization and discrete logarithms on a quantum computer,” *SIAM review*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 303–332, 1999.
- [3] M. A. Nielsen and I. L. Chuang, *Quantum Computation and Quantum Information: 10th Anniversary Edition*. Cambridge University Press, 2010.
- [4] T. Lubinski, S. Johri, P. Varosy, J. Coleman, L. Zhao, J. Necaie, C. Baldwin, K. Mayer, and T. Proctor, “Application-oriented performance benchmarks for quantum computing,” 10 2021.
- [5] Measuring quantum volume. [Online]. Available: <https://qiskit.org/textbook/ch-quantum-hardware/measuring-quantum-volume.html>
- [6] S. Bravyi, D. Gosset, and R. König, “Quantum advantage with shallow circuits,” *Science*, vol. 362, no. 6412, p. 308–311, Oct 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1126/science.aar3106>
- [7] S. Bravyi, D. Gosset, R. Koenig, and M. Tomamichel, “Quantum advantage with noisy shallow circuits,” *Nature Physics*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1040–1045, 2020.
- [8] A. Frisk Kockum, “Quantum optics with artificial atoms,” Ph.D. dissertation, 12 2014.
- [9] Qiskit tutorials, the density matrix & mixed states. [Online]. Available: <https://qiskit.org/textbook/ch-quantum-hardware/density-matrix.html>
- [10] M. Walter. Quantum correlations, non-local games, rigidity. [Online]. Available: <https://michaelwalter.info/physics491/>
- [11] G. Brassard, A. Broadbent, and A. Tapp, “Quantum pseudo-telepathy,” *Foundations of Physics*, vol. 35, no. 11, pp. 1877–1907, 2005.
- [12] Qiskit tutorials, device backend noise model simulations. [Online]. Available: https://qiskit.org/documentation/tutorials/simulators/2_device_noise_simulation.html
- [13] K. Georgopoulos, C. Emary, and P. Zuliani, “Modeling and simulating the noisy behavior of near-term quantum computers,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 104, no. 6, Dec 2021. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.104.062432>
- [14] QuTech. cQASM: Error models. [Online]. Available: <https://www.quantum-inspire.com/kbase/cqasm-error-models/>
- [15] S. Johnstun and J.-F. Van Huele, “Understanding and compensating for noise on IBM quantum computers,” *American Journal of Physics*, vol. 89, no. 10, pp. 935–942, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1119/10.0006204>
- [16] IBM Quantum Services, ibmq_toronto. [Online]. Available: <https://quantum-computing.ibm.com/services?services=systems>

- [17] N. M. Linke, D. Maslov, M. Roetteler, S. Debnath, C. Figgatt, K. A. Landsman, K. Wright, and C. Monroe, “Experimental comparison of two quantum computing architectures,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 114, no. 13, pp. 3305–3310, mar 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1618020114>

Appendices

A Deriving diagonal representation of Pauli-X gate

For matrix representation A of a single-qubit gate, its diagonal representation is expressed as [3]:

$$A = \sum_i \lambda_i |v_i\rangle\langle v_i| \quad (92)$$

where λ_i is the eigenvalue of A and $|v_i\rangle$ is the Z-basis states of a qubit or the corresponding eigenvectors of λ_i .

λ_i and $|v_i\rangle$ should satisfy:

$$A|v_i\rangle = \lambda_i|v_i\rangle \quad (93)$$

Another form of Eq.(93) is:

$$(A - \lambda_i I)|v_i\rangle = 0 \quad (94)$$

Taking the Pauli-X gate in Eq.(25) as example to illustrate how the diagonal representation is derived, the characteristic function $c(\lambda_i)$ can first be found as:

$$c(\lambda_i) = \det |X - \lambda_i I| = \det \left| \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_i & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_i \end{pmatrix} \right| = \det \left| \begin{pmatrix} -\lambda_i & 1 \\ 1 & -\lambda_i \end{pmatrix} \right| = \lambda_i^2 - 1 \quad (95)$$

where the notation “ \det ” is the function that outputs the determinant.

Equate Eq.(95) to 0, the solutions of the equation will be the eigenvalue λ_i of X :

$$\lambda_i^2 - 1 = 0 \quad (96)$$

$$\lambda_0 = 1, \quad \lambda_1 = -1 \quad (97)$$

Then, substitute X and Eq.(97) into Eq.(94),

$$(X - \lambda_0 I)|v_0\rangle = (X - \lambda_1 I)|v_1\rangle = 0 \quad (98)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} d_1 \\ d_2 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (99)$$

$$c_1 = c_2, \quad d_1 = -d_2 \quad (100)$$

where $|v_0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \end{pmatrix}$ and $|v_1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} d_1 \\ d_2 \end{pmatrix}$.

Since $|v_0\rangle$ and $|v_1\rangle$ have norm equal to 1,

$$\| |v_0\rangle \| = \sqrt{c_1^2 + c_2^2} = 1, \quad \| |v_1\rangle \| = \sqrt{d_1^2 + d_2^2} = 1 \quad (101)$$

substitute Eq.(101) into Eq.(100), values of c_1 , c_2 and d_1 , d_2 are obtained:

$$c_1, c_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad d_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, d_2 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (102)$$

Thus, the eigenvectors $|v_i\rangle$ of X are:

$$|v_0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle), \quad |v_1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle) \quad (103)$$

Finally, using Eq.(92), the diagonal representation of X can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= \lambda_0|v_0\rangle\langle v_0| + \lambda_1|v_1\rangle\langle v_1| \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\langle 0| + \langle 1|) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\langle 0| - \langle 1|) \\ &= |0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 0| \end{aligned} \quad (104)$$

B Transforming measuring basis from Z to X

To transform the measuring basis from Z-basis into X-basis, a Hadamard gate is used. The quantum circuit for this transformation is shown by Figure B.1.

Figure B.1: Quantum circuit for transforming measuring basis from Z to X

The initial state $|\psi_0\rangle$ is shown by Eq.(17). The state $|\psi_1\rangle$ prior to measuring in Z-basis is therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_1\rangle &= H|\psi_0\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 0| + |0\rangle\langle 1| + |1\rangle\langle 1|)(a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}[(a+b)|0\rangle + (a-b)|1\rangle] \end{aligned} \quad (105)$$

Since X-basis states are $|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ and $|-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$ as shown by Eq.(19).

If $|\psi_0\rangle = |+\rangle$, then $a, b = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$. Substitute into Eq.(105):

$$|\psi_1\rangle = |0\rangle \quad (106)$$

If $|\psi_0\rangle = |-\rangle$, then $a = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $b = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$. Substitute into Eq.(105):

$$|\psi_1\rangle = |1\rangle \quad (107)$$

Eq.(106) and Eq.(107) show that by making such transformation, Z-basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are replaced by X-basis states $|+\rangle$ and $|-\rangle$. In other word, the qubit with state $|\psi_0\rangle$ is measured in X-basis now, which has the same meaning as measuring the qubit with state $|\psi_1\rangle$ in Z-basis.

C Transpiled SQCs for all combinations of α_1 and β_1

Figure C.1: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=01$ and $\beta_1=01$

global phase : $\frac{3\pi}{4}$

Figure C.2: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=01$ and $\beta_1=10$

Figure C.3: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=01$ and $\beta_1=11$

global phase : $\frac{3\pi}{4}$

Figure C.5: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=10$ and $\beta_1=10$

Figure C.6: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=10$ and $\beta_1=11$

global phase : $\frac{5\pi}{4}$

Figure C.7: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=11$ and $\beta_1=01$

global phase : $\frac{3\pi}{4}$

Figure C.8: Transpiled SQC for $\alpha_1=11$ and $\beta_1=10$

D Error parameter analysis diagrams for all combinations of α_1 and β_1

Figure D.1: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=01$ and $\beta_1=01$

Figure D.2: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=01$ and $\beta_1=10$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 01, \beta_1 = 11$) SQC

Figure D.3: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=01$ and $\beta_1=11$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 10, \beta_1 = 01$) SQC

Figure D.4: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=10$ and $\beta_1=01$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 10, \beta_1 = 10$) SQC

Figure D.5: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=10$ and $\beta_1=10$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 10, \beta_1 = 11$) SQC

Figure D.6: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=10$ and $\beta_1=11$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 11, \beta_1 = 01$) SQC

Figure D.7: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=11$ and $\beta_1=01$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 11, \beta_1 = 10$) SQC

Figure D.8: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=11$ and $\beta_1=10$

Noises in ($\alpha_1 = 11, \beta_1 = 11$) SQC

Figure D.9: Error parameter analysis diagram for $\alpha_1=11$ and $\beta_1=11$